

Viscometric Study of Clay-humus Complexes

B. C. Sen

Viscometric studies of clay-humus complexes have been made in the presence of different cations. The η_{sp}/C vs. C graphs are found to be linear, especially at high dilutions. An attempt has been made to obtain a rough idea about the molecular weights of the products of the reaction between clay and humus, using Staudinger's equation.

Clays are crystalline aggregates. Humic acid may perhaps be considered as mixtures of high polymers. Viscosity measurements have been undertaken with a view to obtain evidence of the interaction between clay and humic acid, if any. Myres (*Soil Sci.*, 1937, **44**, 331) observed a considerable change in the time of flow of colloidal clay when it was mixed with organic colloidal sols; this change could not be explained by assuming simple mechanical mixing.

EXPERIMENTAL

An Ostwald viscometer in its simplest form was used. The time of flow of water at the temperature of experiment (30°) was 45 secs. Crude humic acid was extracted from Siliguri soil from Darjeeling, West Bengal by repeated treatment with $(N/2)Na_2CO_3$ solution. From the alkali leachate humic acid was coagulated by HCl (dil.) and finally purified by electro dialysis. The clay fractions ($<1\mu$) from four different soil samples were collected in the usual way. The clay suspension was then coagulated with HCl (dil.), thoroughly treated with H_2O_2 to destroy organic matter, and finally electro dialysed to obtain H-clay. The humic acid and clay fractions were mixed in the proportions of 1:60 in presence of different ions and about a week's time was allowed for the reaction to proceed. The time of flow of the different mixtures was measured in the same Ostwald viscometer at a constant temperature of 30° . The viscosities of different clay-humic acid mixtures in presence of metal and H^+ ions were measured with various amounts of solid matter present in the suspension and the values of specific viscosities were calculated. Similar viscosity data for clays in presence of different ions, but without humus, were also obtained for comparison with the above results. The variation of reduced viscosities of all the systems with dilution was followed graphically by plotting η_{sp}/C vs. C .

DISCUSSION

The viscosity of dilute suspensions of rigid spherical particles, which are wetted by the solvent, is given by Einstein's equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\Phi + 4\Phi^2 + 5.3\Phi^3$$

from which $\eta_{sp} = (\eta/\eta_0 - 1) = 2.5\Phi$, for small Φ (Φ =total volume of suspended particle/total volume of suspension). For non-spherical particles at higher concentrations, Guth *et al.* (*Kolloid Z.*, 1936, **74**, 266) obtained the following relation,

$$\eta = \eta_0 (1 + 2.5\Phi + 14.1\Phi^2 + \dots)$$

so that $\eta_{sp} = 2.5\Phi + 14.1\Phi^2$. If the unit of concentration is g./100 c.c. of suspension, $(\eta_{sp}/C)C \rightarrow 0 = (\eta)$, called the intrinsic viscosity, is equal to $0.025V$, where V is the specific volume of the solute. For swelling particles $(\eta) = 0.025SV$, where S is the swelling factor and is equal to effective volume, including bound and trapped solvent, divided by the actual volume. For prolates and oblates, the numerical factor 0.025 will increase according as the axial ratio becomes greater than unity. The values of (η) for the different systems have been obtained from the plot of η_{sp}/C vs. C , typical graphs of which are shown in Figures 1-4. The (η) values thus obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

CI=Illitic clay from Contai soil.

AGM=Montmorillonite clay from Aquagel.

KI=Illitic clay (with a trace of kaolinite) from Kakdwip soil.

RK=Rajmahal kaolinite.

SHm=Humic acid from Siliguri soil.

	CI.	AGM.	KI.	RK.
Humic acid	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21
Clay	0.08	0.29	0.155	0.09
Clay + Ca ²⁺	0.09	0.33	0.20	0.11
Clay + Mg ²⁺	0.10	0.35	0.22	0.11
Clay + Al ³⁺	0.11	0.38	0.24	0.12
Clay + Fe ³⁺	0.12	0.40	0.24	0.13
SHm + clay + H ⁺ (1:60)	0.095	0.225	0.10	0.105
SHm + clay + Ca ²⁺	0.18	0.37	0.19	0.120
SHm + clay + Mg ²⁺	0.19	0.46	0.20	0.145
SHm + clay + Al ³⁺	0.22	0.72	0.22	0.160
SHm + clay + Fe ³⁺	0.23	0.80	0.23	0.170

If the density of humic acid is of the order of 1.2, S , the swelling factor=10.0, assuming spherical particles. For clays the density is of the order of 2.5 and S is of the order of 22, which indicates a much higher swelling than that of humic acid. For clay: humic acid ratio of 1:60, used in these experiments, the density of the mixtures may be taken to be equal to that of the clay itself. Consequently, any value of (η) greater than that of the clay would indicate extra swelling and/or inclusion of trapped water. In fact, except the AGM-SHm mixtures and KI-SHm mixtures containing H⁺ ions, all the other systems indicate strong swelling and/or inclusion of trapped water. The values of S , calculated on the basis of $V = 1/2.5$, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

	CI.	AGM.	KI.	RK.
Clay	8.0	29.0	15.5	9.0
Clay + SHM + H ⁺	9.5(35)	22.5(55)	10.0(32)	10.5(23)
Clay + SHM + Ca ²⁺	18.0(46)	37.0(73)	19.0(42)	12.0(32)
Clay + SHM + Mg ²⁺	19.0(55)	46.0(82)	20.0(48)	14.5(37)
Clay + SHM + Al ³⁺	22.0(54)	72.0(82)	22.0(48)	16.0(36)
Clay + SHM + Fe ³⁺	23.0(58)	90.0(82)	23.0(50)	17.0(38)

VISCOMETRIC STUDY OF CLAY-HUMUS COMPLEX

FIG. 1. AGM-clay—SHm mixtures in presence of diff. ions (SHm: AGM=1:60).

FIG. 2. CI-clay—SHm mixtures in presence of diff. ions (SHm: CI=1:60).

FIG. 3. AGM-clay + metal ions (without humic acid).

FIG. 4. CI-clay + metal ions (without humic acid).

The figures within brackets in Table II give the percentage of humic acid combined with clay at 1:60 ratio, which have been observed from the study of its adsorption on different clays (Sen, this *Journal*, 1960 **37**, 793).

It will be observed from the above figures that the swelling factor increases, with the exception of AGM and KI mentioned above, in the order: $H^+ < Ca^{2+} < Mg^{2+} < Al^{3+} < Fe^{3+}$. But the percentages of humic acid combined are in the order: $H^+ < Ca^{2+} < Mg^{2+} \approx Al^{3+} \approx Fe^{3+}$. It may be therefore that the increase in hydrodynamic volume or the swelling factor is not entirely due to the clay-humus complex, but may be also partly due to hydration of the ions themselves, which are likely to form flocculent masses with the clays or the clay-humus complexes. It will, however, be noted from the data in Table I that only with AGM and KI, the cations have an appreciable effect on (η) , hence on the swelling or hydration of the clay. For the other clays, there is hardly any influence of cations on swelling.

If it is assumed that the flocculating effect of ions, *i. e.*, the secondary effect of ions causing increase in (η) , is not exhibited to any marked extent in presence of Ca^{2+} ions, which mainly co-ordinate the clay and humic acid particles to form the complexes, the values of (η) may be used to get an idea of the molecular weight of such complexes. The molecular weight of humic acid (S. A. Waksman, "Humus") has been estimated at about 1500. This would correspond to a value of K in Staudinger's equation, $(\eta) = K.M^\alpha$, of the order of 5×10^{-3} , if α is assumed to be equal to 0.5. For clays and clay—humus complexes, if K is taken to be one tenth of that of humic acid, *i. e.*, $= 5 \times 10^{-4}$, M is of the order of 3×10^5 or more. Unless verified by independent methods, these values are of little use. Taking the values of $K = 5 \times 10^{-4}$ for AGM clay—humic acid mixtures, the molecular weight of the complex in presence of Fe^{3+} ions is of the order of 2.5×10^6 , which is ten times larger than that of AGM clay itself. This may be taken to suggest that fairly large aggregates are formed between clay and humic acid.

With AGM clay—SHm mixtures, the molecular weight of the clay—humic acid complex in presence of H^+ ions appears to be less than that of the clay itself, although greater than that of crude humic acid. AGM clay is highly hydrated as the high value of hydrodynamic volume in Table II shows; a combination with humic acid in presence of H^+ ions probably reduces the number of entrapped solvent molecules and hence the value of (η) . In presence of Ca^{2+} ions, the hydration considerably increases and therefore also the values of (η) . So also is the case of KI clay.

The above calculation, owing to obvious limitations and lack of supporting data for the constants of Staudinger's equation, leads us to no definite and concrete understanding of the molecular species. There is, however, one point to be noted. The linear nature of the $\eta_{sp}C$ vs. C graphs, especially at high dilution, suggests strongly that the products of the interaction are quite stable and do not disaggregate on dilution, thus behaving more or less as molecular species.

Thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee, D.Sc., Professor of Macromolecules, Indian Association for Cultivation of Science, for his guidance and valuable suggestions and to Prof. P. C. Rakshit, Ph.D., Head of the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta, for his continued interest and giving laboratory facilities.